

GREENVERSITY

GREENVERSITY PATHWAY

**Implementation procedures for educators
and accreditation bodies**

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2	University of Jyväskylä	JYU	FI
3	University of Burgundy	UB	FR
4	The Valencian Agency for Assessment and Prospective	AVAP	ES
5	The “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu	ULBS	RO
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GREENIVERSITY PATHWAY

IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURES FOR EDUCATORS AND ACCREDITATION BODIES

DISCLAIMER

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document serves as a **guidance framework and sets recommendations for European higher education evaluation and accreditation bodies**, outlining how sustainability and green competences can be systematically integrated into the quality assurance and verification processes of university degree programmes. It has been developed within the framework of the **GREENIVERSITY Project**, a three-year European initiative dedicated to embedding the GreenComp: **European Sustainability Competence Framework (GreenComp)** into higher education systems.

The central mission of GREENIVERSITY is to empower universities, educators, and students with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to lead sustainable transformations across society. By developing structured methodologies, training programs, and student-led initiatives, the project aims to make green competences a core and measurable component of higher education throughout Europe.

The document proposes that **quality assurance and accreditation agencies** play a key role in this transformation. Their procedures—particularly those related to **programme verification, monitoring, modification, and accreditation of the higher education degrees**—can serve as critical entry points for embedding sustainability principles into institutional practices. Through the adoption of GreenComp, agencies can:

- **Standardise approaches to sustainability education** across diverse institutions and disciplines, ensuring coherence and consistency in how green competences are defined, taught, and assessed.
- **Enhance learning outcomes** by promoting the inclusion of sustainability-oriented objectives in programme design and student assessment, thus equipping graduates with the essential knowledge, skills, and competences to address environmental, economic and societal challenges.
- **Support the European Union's Green Deal and sustainability objectives** by aligning higher education evaluation frameworks with EU sustainability policies, encouraging universities to act as drivers of ecological transition.
- **Prepare future leaders for systemic change**, emphasising not only technical expertise but also ethical reasoning, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving—competences central to the GreenComp framework.

Ultimately, **this guide contributes to building a shared European standard for sustainable higher education**, positioning universities as key actors in the transition toward a greener, fairer, and more resilient future. It calls on quality assurance bodies, policymakers, and educational institutions to collaborate in embedding the GreenComp framework at all levels of academic governance and evaluation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
ENQA	European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
LO	Learning Outcomes
LO. K	Learning Outcomes, Knowledge
LO. S	Learning Outcomes, Skills
LO. C	Learning Outcomes, Competences

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1 Framework of the report

The **GREENVERSITY Project**, funded under the Erasmus+ Cooperation Partnerships in Higher Education (KA220-HED), seeks to strengthen the integration of sustainability competences across university programs through strategic frameworks, sustainability-driven educational programs and institutional collaboration. **GREENVERSITY builds on the GreenComp Framework, the European reference for sustainability competences (Bianchi et al, 2024)** to guide its actions and outcomes. The project's overarching goal is to foster transformative learning environments that enable both educators and students to develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes, necessary to contribute actively to a sustainable future.

In particular, the **Greenversity PATHWAY** serves as both a **conceptual and operational guide for embedding sustainability competences into the verification, monitoring, modification, and accreditation processes of university educational programmes**. Its overarching objective is to support quality assurance agencies, universities, and academic governance bodies in aligning institutional evaluation practices with the strategic priorities of the European Green Deal and the broader transition toward sustainable higher education systems.

This report is intimately connected to the **GREENVERSITY CORE, the Framework of Sustainability Competences in Higher Education**, a comprehensive model that translates the high-level competences of **GreenComp** into clear, measurable learning objectives **tailored to higher education (Echegoyen-Sanz et al, 2025)**. Designed to be transversal, the framework seeks to be relevant to all academic disciplines and degree levels, ensuring that sustainability competences are embedded across the entire university ecosystem.

The present document, i.e., the Greenversity PATHWAY, is structured to provide a comprehensive framework for action. The initial section, which outlines the aim, establishes the objectives of the report and clarifies its intended contribution to embedding GreenComp within higher education quality assurance and accreditation frameworks. It defines the scope of the proposal and highlights its potential impact on governance structures, curriculum design, and the achievement of student learning outcomes. The methodology details the approach adopted in the development of the framework, including rigorous document analysis, benchmarking of European quality assurance systems, and participatory consultation with experts and institutional stakeholders across the Greenversity network. Following this, the report identifies the target audiences, specifying the key actors who may apply or benefit from its recommendations, including accreditation agencies, university leadership, program coordinators, and academic committees responsible for curriculum design and assessment. At the core of the report is the **development of the Greenversity Pathway**, which explains how to implement and obtain recognition of the implementation of the GreenComp, and outlines the procedural and evaluative steps through which the quality of the academic programmes are reviewed and assessed. This section details the proposed evaluation criteria, introduces a traffic-light system (green, yellow, red) for assessing the level of integration, specifies a minimum of sustainability requirements at the course level, and establishes the types of evidence institutions must provide to demonstrate compliance with the GreenComp framework. It also presents alternatives, as for example, more curriculum-integrated approaches of assessment that adapt the traditional 1–10 grading system to better reflect levels of sustainability integration. Complementing this, the document provides a short and overall review of the main quality assessment procedures, splitting the information into two subheadings, one for the Ex-ante accreditation and the other for Ex-post accreditation. This report further includes practical resources to facilitate effective implementation. Section of **tools for evaluation committees** provides templates, rubrics, checklists, and guidelines to ensure consistent alignment with GreenComp principles and robust interpretation of evidence submitted by programs. The section on **tips for implementation** provides actionable recommendations for institutions, highlighting strategies for faculty engagement, student participation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and institutional support to maximise the impact of sustainability integration. Finally, the **conclusions** synthesise the key insights and reaffirm the strategic importance of embedding sustainability within higher education evaluation and accreditation systems.

1.1 Aim

The primary aim of this report is to provide a comprehensive framework to support the systematic integration of the European Sustainability Competence Framework (GreenComp) into higher education programmes, while simultaneously enhancing the effectiveness and transparency of quality assurance procedures. On the one hand, the report seeks to facilitate universities the task of incorporating GreenComp competences into their degree programs, offering clear guidance on how to align curricula, teaching methodologies, learning outcomes, and assessment systems with recognised sustainability standards. By doing so, the report supports institutions in embedding sustainability as a core dimension of programme design and delivery, ensuring that students acquire the skills, knowledge, and attitudes required to actively contribute to sustainable development and the green transition.

On the other hand, the report aims to support the decision-making processes of evaluation and accreditation bodies by providing a structured approach for assessing the integration of sustainability learning outcomes within academic programmes. This includes guidance on evaluating the alignment of learning outcomes and competences with GreenComp, the suitability and effectiveness of teaching and learning methodologies, the robustness of assessment and evaluation systems, and the implementation of quality monitoring mechanisms. By linking these dimensions, the report ensures that sustainability integration is not only encouraged at the programmatic level but is also systematically evaluated, verified, and monitored as part of existing accreditation procedures.

In essence, the report serves a dual purpose: to enable universities to embed sustainability meaningfully and coherently into their curricula, and to equip evaluation agencies with the tools and criteria needed to make evidence-based, transparent, and consistent decisions regarding programme verification, monitoring, modification, and accreditation. This dual focus ensures that the GreenComp framework becomes an operational and measurable standard across European higher education, fostering both educational quality and the development of competences essential for the transition to a sustainable society.

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1.2 Methodology

The methodology underpinning this report has been designed to ensure both conceptual rigor and practical applicability integrating the GreenComp framework into higher education programmes and quality assurance procedures. It combines a structured analytical approach with participatory processes involving key stakeholders across the European higher education landscape.

To achieve this, the GREENVERSITY consortium engaged a diverse network of around **20 experts and stakeholders** representing academia, research institutions, educators, policymakers, and non-governmental organizations from across Europe. Their insights and feedback were gathered through several consultation rounds to ensure the framework's conceptual robustness, inclusiveness, and practical relevance. The development process unfolded through several key phases:

- It began with a **scoping phase**, which included extensive desk research and literature analysis to identify existing models, theories, and best practices in sustainability education and competence-based learning. This resulted in the report “**Use cases to include sustainability competences in higher education**” (Echegoyen-Sanz et al, 2025a), in which orientations and needs were proposed.
- Afterwards, a **consultation to the demand-side with stakeholders from the so-called Triple-Bottom-Line**, i.e., experts in the social, economy and environmental spheres, was carried out, with a focus on the green skills that are required by green hiring practices. This resulted in the report “**Sustainability skills for citizens: demands from the environmental, economic and social spheres**” (Gil et al, 2025), here a connection of required skills with educational programs resulted relevant to induce the cultivation of sustainable leadership and interdisciplinary problem-solving

Following this, the GREENVERSITY team developed the **GREENVERSITY CORE Framework** (Echegoyen-Sanz et al, 2025b), offering universities a coherent, adaptable, and user-friendly model for embedding sustainability competences across disciplines and fostering systemic thinking for a sustainable future.

- In order to contextualise the PATHWAY in the EU context, several European countries have begun to develop regulatory frameworks that enable educational institutions —particularly universities— to embed these competences in their curricula, in many cases establishing their inclusion as a formal requirement. Within the framework of this project, the regulations of the six countries involved that oblige the incorporation of sustainability competences into study programmes were benchmarked.
- Subsequently, iterative virtual workshops and meetings focused on the thorough understanding of the Quality assurance procedures and the needs and barriers to implement the Pathway, which offered the **initial proposal** of methods and criteria. A key component of the methodology was stakeholder engagement. This participatory approach ensured that the proposed framework responds to both institutional realities and the operational needs of evaluation bodies. Feedback was sought on criteria for learning outcomes, teaching methodologies, assessment systems, and quality monitoring mechanisms, ensuring that recommendations are actionable, measurable, and aligned with European higher education standards.
- Next, **collaborative workshops** brought together experts in design, plan and implantation of university degrees were performed, in order to pulse interest, and gather gains and possible barriers.
- Finally, the methodology emphasizes the operationalization of GreenComp competences through a clear structure for evaluation and monitoring. This includes the definition of minimum requirements per programme, suggested types of evidence for verification, and a traffic-light assessment system to categorise levels of sustainability integration. Hence, the Pathway underwent continuous

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refinement through **ongoing feedback and validation activities with partner institutions and external experts**. This process help ensured that the final GREENIVERSITY PATHWAY could be sound and operationally feasible, offering universities and accreditation bodies a user-friendly model for embedding sustainability competences across disciplines and university structures.

1.3 Target audiences and potential uses

This report is designed to address the needs of multiple stakeholders involved in the design, evaluation, and accreditation of higher education programmes, with a particular focus on those responsible for **quality assurance** and the integration of sustainability competences within universities. The framework and recommendations presented herein are intended to be practical, actionable, and adaptable across diverse institutional contexts, ensuring that both policy and operational objectives are effectively met.

At the forefront, the primary target audiences are **quality assurance agencies** and **evaluators** responsible for verification, monitoring, modifications, and accreditation processes. These stakeholders play a critical role in ensuring that programmes meet established standards of academic quality, and the integration of sustainability competences represents a growing dimension of these standards. The report provides these agencies and evaluators with **structured guidance, evaluation criteria, evidence requirements, and practical assessment tools** to support decision-making in programme verification, monitoring, modification, and accreditation. By aligning their evaluation procedures with the GreenComp framework, quality assurance bodies can ensure consistency, transparency, and rigor in the assessment of sustainability integration across European higher education institutions.

In addition, **universities** represent a key target audience for the report. This includes **university leadership, programme coordinators, curriculum designers, and faculty members**, all of whom are responsible for embedding sustainability into degree programs.

Ultimately, **students** are defined as the final beneficiaries of its implementation, as they are the primary recipients of the educational outcomes derived from these sustainability-oriented initiatives. The report offers universities a clear roadmap for incorporating GreenComp competences into their curricula, aligning learning outcomes with teaching methodologies, assessment strategies, and internal quality assurance mechanisms. By following the recommendations provided, universities can systematically demonstrate compliance with accreditation criteria, enhance program quality, and ensure that students acquire the knowledge, skills, and competences necessary to contribute to sustainable development and the European Green Deal objectives.

While the report is primarily directed at these two groups, it also provides relevant insights for other stakeholders involved in higher education governance, policy development, and quality monitoring. By addressing both **the supply side (universities)** and **the regulatory side (agencies and evaluators)**, the report ensures that the integration of sustainability competences is supported by a coherent, evidence-based, and mutually reinforcing framework, fostering a shared understanding and consistent implementation of GreenComp across European higher education institutions.

1.4 National regulatory frameworks

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Across the partners of the Greeniversity project (Spain, Finland, France, Romania, Ireland and Portugal), higher education is regulated through comprehensive national legal frameworks that define degree structures, accreditation processes and the mandatory use of learning outcomes. **In all cases, degree programmes are organised within Bachelor, Master and Doctoral cycles, use ECTS credits, and are aligned with National Qualifications Frameworks that correspond to the European Qualifications Framework** (typically Level 6 for Bachelor, Level 7 for Master and Level 8 for Doctorate).

Accreditation and quality assurance are assessed by national agencies (such as FINEEC in Finland, HCERES in France, ARACIS in Romania and A3ES in Portugal, **all of them following ENQA recommendations**), which require programs to demonstrate coherence between learning outcomes, degree level, curriculum design and labour market needs.

Learning Outcomes (LOs) are legally embedded and competence-based across all partner countries, generally defined as statements describing what graduates know, understand and are able to do at the end of a learning process, expressed in terms of knowledge, skills and responsibility/autonomy/competences. Their formulation is guided by national and European frameworks and operationalised through program descriptions and compulsory course syllabi, which align teaching methods and assessment with intended outcomes. Assessment practices combine examinations, coursework, projects, and final theses, with increasing emphasis on continuous and formative assessment. Overall, these regulatory environments strongly support outcome-oriented, transparent and internationally comparable higher education, while also encouraging responsiveness to societal challenges, employability and, increasingly, sustainability and green competences, creating a solid regulatory foundation for the objectives of the Greeniversity project.

Due to the fact that the inclusion of sustainability in degree programmes is normatively prescribed, albeit with varying levels of stringency and specific requirements across different regulations, all accredited programs are required to define sustainability learning outcomes across knowledge, skills, and competence, with competence explicitly encompassing responsibility, autonomy, and the capacity to act appropriately within social and professional contexts. This outcome-based structure implicitly requires the integration of sustainability-related dimensions, such as ethical awareness, social responsibility, and long-term impact. **Alignment with European frameworks further reinforces this obligation, as sustainability and responsible citizenship are core elements of European competence-based education.** For the Greeniversity project, this means that sustainability must be embedded within competence-oriented learning outcomes rather than treated as an optional or isolated topic.

When it comes to **specific aspects at national level:**

- In Spain, sustainability is explicitly embedded in higher education through recent structural reforms of the university system. National legislation requires degree programmes to be designed using a learning-outcomes and competence-based approach aligned with the Spanish Qualifications Framework for Higher Education and the European Qualifications Framework. Sustainability, social responsibility, ethical commitment, equality, and environmental awareness are identified as transversal competences that must be integrated across curricula. Universities are explicitly tasked with contributing to sustainable development, social cohesion, and ecological transition as part of their public mission. For Greeniversity, the Spanish regulatory context offers a strong and explicit mandate for sustainability integration. Greeniversity pathways align directly with national requirements to incorporate sustainability as a transversal learning outcome across degree programmes. By structuring sustainability competences in a clear, assessable, and transferable way, Greeniversity supports Spanish universities in meeting legal obligations while enhancing coherence, innovation, and European comparability in sustainability education.
- In Finland, sustainability is strongly embedded in higher education through legal requirements that education respond to societal needs, working life demands, and global challenges. Degree

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programmes must be designed around competence-based learning outcomes that integrate knowledge, skills, and responsibility and autonomy. This framework creates a clear obligation to address sustainable development, ethical professional practice, and societal impact as integral components of learning. The strong linkage between higher education, labour market relevance, and societal responsibility makes sustainability a structural expectation rather than an optional thematic addition. Within the Greeniversity context, sustainability aligns directly with the Finnish requirement that graduates demonstrate readiness to address complex, real-world challenges. Greeniversity learning pathways naturally fit the Finnish emphasis on applied knowledge, lifelong learning, and societal relevance. By embedding sustainability within competence-based outcomes and assessment practices, Greeniversity supports national legal expectations and quality assurance standards while reinforcing Finland's strategic commitment to sustainable development.

- In France, sustainability is increasingly explicit within higher education policy and practice, particularly through the integration of transversal competences in national degree frameworks. Learning outcomes are defined in competence-based terms and increasingly include ethical responsibility, social engagement, and environmental awareness. National strategies for ecological transition and institutional obligations related to sustainable development and social responsibility further strengthen the expectation that higher education contributes actively to sustainability goals. Accreditation and evaluation processes require programmes to demonstrate coherence with public policy priorities, including ecological and societal transition. For Greeniversity, the French context provides a highly supportive environment. Sustainability-oriented learning outcomes are not only compatible with national standards but are increasingly expected in programme design and evaluation. Greeniversity can therefore function as a concrete operationalisation of national sustainability objectives, reinforcing transversal competences, and aligning academic learning with ecological transition policies and institutional sustainability strategies.
- In Romania, sustainability is embedded through the legally binding definition of learning outcomes, which explicitly includes responsibility and autonomy alongside knowledge and skills. This framing obliges higher education programmes to address social responsibility, ethical conduct, and the broader impact of professional activity. The distinction between professional and transversal competences further reinforces the expectation that graduates develop the capacity to act responsibly within society and the labour market. Although sustainability is not always explicitly named, it is clearly implied through these mandatory responsibility-oriented descriptors. For Greeniversity, this framework allows sustainability to be fully integrated within transversal competences and programme-level learning outcomes. Greeniversity pathways can explicitly articulate sustainability as an expression of responsibility, autonomy, and societal engagement, thereby strengthening programme coherence and supporting accreditation requirements. In this way, Greeniversity enhances the visibility and practical implementation of sustainability within Romanian higher education.
- In Ireland, Greeniversity pathways implemented must demonstrate alignment with NFQ levels and ECTS requirements while clearly articulating how learners develop responsible, value-driven, and future-oriented capacities. This ensures regulatory compliance while strengthening coherence with European sustainability competence frameworks such as GreenComp.
- In Portugal, sustainability is embedded in higher education through the legally mandated shift from content-based teaching to competence-based learning. Learning outcomes must encompass knowledge, skills, and attitudes, with attitudes explicitly referring to responsibility and autonomy. This framework requires programmes to demonstrate societal relevance, ethical awareness, and the capacity of graduates to apply learning in real-world contexts. Accreditation processes reinforce these transversal dimensions, making sustainability an integral component of educational quality and relevance. For Greeniversity, the Portuguese framework provides a clear foundation for embedding sustainability within programme design and learning outcomes. By aligning sustainability with responsibility, autonomy, and applied competence development, Greeniversity

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pathways directly support national accreditation expectations. The project therefore strengthens the link between academic learning, societal needs, and sustainable development priorities in Portuguese higher education.

To sum up, across all Greeniversity partner countries, **sustainability is embedded as a core expectation within higher education through competence-based learning outcomes, alignment with national and European qualifications frameworks, and accreditation requirements focused on societal relevance and responsibility.** Although the degree of explicitness varies, all systems require graduates to demonstrate responsibility, autonomy, ethical awareness, and the ability to address complex societal and professional challenges. Sustainability therefore emerges as a shared structural principle rather than an optional thematic addition. Greeniversity builds these commonalities by making sustainability explicit, coherent, and assessable across national contexts. The project acts as a unifying transnational framework that translates existing regulatory obligations into a shared educational pathway, strengthening compliance, comparability, and long-term impact while supporting European objectives for sustainable development and responsible citizenship.

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2 The GREENVERSITY PATHWAY

As previously introduced, the **GREENVERSITY Project** is an **Erasmus+ Cooperation Partnership in Higher Education** (KA220-HED) focused on embedding sustainability competences thoroughly across university programs by leveraging innovative pedagogical tools, strategic frameworks, and institutional collaboration.

GREENVERSITY bases its approach on the GreenComp framework to guide its activities and objectives into the Higher Education system. By translating policy and frameworks into practical strategies for course design, curriculum development, and institutional accreditation, GREENVERSITY aspires to contribute to lasting change in the structure and culture of Higher Education Institutions across Europe, equipping future leaders to advance sustainability comprehensively and effectively within society.

In the core section of the present document, the **GREENVERSITY PATHWAY** outlines the criteria, procedures, and evaluation system for academic programs to achieve formal quality assessment. This pathway is designed to facilitate the incorporation of GreenComp competences by universities while simultaneously supporting quality assurance agencies and evaluators in assessing alignment with learning outcomes, teaching methodologies, assessment systems, and monitoring mechanisms.

In this section, tools are provided to be incorporated into the quality evaluation processes of quality assurance agencies and therefore in their own guidelines.

2.1 Typology and incorporation of the Greenversity Learning Outcomes

Across the Greenversity partners, higher education regulations establish a common framework based on ECTS (European Credit Transfer System), structured degree cycles, national qualification frameworks aligned with the EQF (European Qualifications Framework), and rigorous accreditation and quality assurance systems. These regulations require clearly defined, competence-based learning outcomes linked to labour market needs, social relevance and international comparability, ensuring transparency and consistency across higher education systems. Learning outcomes are legally required to be structured around integrated components of knowledge, skills, and competences (or equivalent descriptors such as responsibilities or attitudes), ensuring transparency, comparability, and relevance to societal and labour market needs. Within this common framework, sustainability is embedded as a transversal and mandatory dimension of learning outcomes, whether explicitly named or implicitly integrated through requirements related to ethical responsibility, social engagement, environmental awareness, and long-term societal impact.

National quality assurance and accreditation agencies consistently evaluate programmes on the coherence, clarity, and assessability of these learning outcomes, as well as their alignment with qualification levels and public policy priorities. **Greenversity operationalises these shared regulatory principles by incorporating sustainability as a cross-cutting learning outcome typology that is fully aligned with national qualification levels and accreditation standards.** Rather than introducing an external or additional requirement, Greenversity makes explicit what is already structurally required across partner systems: the development of graduates capable of responsible, autonomous, and sustainability-oriented action in complex real-world contexts. By framing sustainability within competence-based learning outcomes that are measurable, transferable, and aligned with the European Qualifications Framework, Greenversity supports national evaluation agencies in recognising compliance, comparability, and added value, while strengthening the coherence and visibility of sustainability competences within higher education programmes.

As is known, Greencomp competences, which nowadays are mostly named as learning outcomes in higher education degrees, are structured into a set of competence areas, each subdivided into specific

competences, as shown in Table 1. To ensure effective integration, these competences must be incorporated into core or mandatory courses, ensuring that all students encounter them. **In this sense, the recommendation is that programmes must include, at least, 8 of the 12 competences, covering at least one competence from each competence area.**

Table1: Twelve GreenComp Competences in Four Competence Areas

EMBODYING SUSTAINABILITY VALUES	EMBRACING COMPLEXITY IN SUSTAINABILITY	ENVISIONING SUSTAINABILITY FUTURES	ACTING FOR SUSTAINABILITY
Valuing sustainability	Systems thinking	Futures literacy	Political agency
Supporting fairness	Critical thinking	Adaptability	Collective action
Promoting nature	Problem framing	Exploratory thinking	Individual initiative

2.2. Evaluation system

To guarantee that students achieve the intended learning outcomes, a robust evaluation system is essential. **Each of the eight selected competences must be evaluated in two different mandatory courses, ensuring that their transversal nature is demonstrated across multiple disciplinary perspectives.** Consequently, evaluation is conducted across sixteen courses (two per competence). In cases where it is not feasible to select sixteen courses, a single course may assess up to two competences.

Each of the twelve learning outcomes is further broken down into Knowledge, Skills, and Competences, resulting in, at least, **24 learning outcomes to be assessed** (minimum of eight outcomes × three components). The development and definition of each outcome follow a standardised template (see Table 2), which records the competence area, selected learning outcomes, courses in which they are included, semester of delivery, and the breakdown of knowledge, skills, and attitudes for each course.

The evaluation of learning outcomes can be integrated with ordinary course assessments, using the same tools employed in each course. That is, it can be included as an exam, a part of an exam, a deliverable, a project, etc. That is to say, no extra load is necessarily a must, but a wider perspective. Each learning outcome score across its three components—knowledge, skills, and attitudes are assessed using a **traffic-light system**:

- **Red:** 0 points
- **Yellow:** 1 point
- **Green:** 2 points

The competence score for a learning outcome ranges from 0 to 6 points. A learning outcome, therefore, is classified as:

- **Red:** 0–1 point
- **Yellow:** 2–4 points
- **Green:** 5–6 points

The final sustainability evaluation of a student in the program is based on the combined scores of all learning outcomes:

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- **Red light:** 0 point
- **Yellow light:** 1 point
- **Green light:** 2 points

Table 2. Learning Outcomes Template

Competence Area	8/12 Competences	Subject1	Subject2	3 LO (Learning Outcomes): knowledges (K), skills (S), competences (C)
Competence area 1: EMBODYING SUSTAINABILITY VALUES				LO.K.
				LO.S.
				LO.C.
Competence area 2: EMBRACING COMPLEXITY IN SUSTAINABILITY				LO.K.
				LO.S.
				LO.C.
Competence area 3: ENVISIONING SUSTAINABILITY FUTURES				LO.K.
				LO.S.
				LO.C.
Competence area 4: ACTING FOR SUSTAINABILITY				LO.K.
				LO.S.
				LO.C.

To achieve an official recognition in a university degree, as a kind of **Green Stamp**, or special certification within the European Supplement to the Title, a student must obtain a **minimum of 16 points out of a maximum of 32 points** (2 points for each of the eight learning outcomes evaluated twice). Additionally, a maximum of **three red lights** is allowed. If programmes include more than eight learning outcomes (up to the full twelve), the **minimum score and maximum allowed red lights** are adjusted accordingly, as suggested in Table 3.

Table 3. Minimum Score and Maximum Red Lights According to Number of Learning Outcomes Included

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Number of Learning Outcomes	Minimum Score	Maximum Red Lights
8	16	3
9	18	4
10	20	4
11	22	5
12	24	5

This system promotes that the integration of **GreenComp competences** is **measurable, transparent, and verifiable**, providing both universities and evaluation agencies with clear criteria for awarding a recognition to degree programs that successfully embed sustainability into their curricula, and students who achieve the required marks.

As a suggestion, although this proposal is straightforward to implement, in systems where evaluation must be conducted on a 10-point scale, for example, the evaluation mechanism could be adapted so that the red light corresponds to a score of 0 to 4.9, the yellow light to 5 to 7.9, and the green light to 8 to 10.

3 Quality assessment processes

The quality assurance procedures that apply to all official university degree **programmes involve verification, monitoring and modification, as well as the renewal of degree accreditation every six years.**

Quality assessment processes distinguish between two modalities of analysis: **prospective (ex-ante)** evaluation and **retrospective (ex-post)** evaluation.

3.1 Prospective evaluation: ex-ante accreditation

In this context, a university may launch a new degree programme through an external ex-ante evaluation procedure that assesses the proposed study plan before its implementation. Each country evaluates whether the verification report submitted by the university meets a set of standards related to the structure of the degree, the study programme and learning outcomes, mobility arrangements, academic staff, material and technical resources, the internal quality assurance system, etc.

3.1.1 Verification of new degrees

In the verification procedure, the university prepares a formal verification report describing the proposed degree, including its academic justification, curriculum design, learning outcomes, admission and mobility schemes, staffing, resources, and quality assurance mechanisms. This report is then subjected to external peer review by evaluators appointed by the Quality Agency, who analyse the coherence and feasibility of the proposal and its alignment with national regulations and the objectives of the European Higher Education Area.

The evaluation focuses on whether the programme design ensures that students can achieve the intended learning outcomes and whether the available resources and organisational arrangements are adequate to support delivery, including aspects such as mobility pathways and the profile and number of staff. This ex-ante assessment concludes with an external report which, if favourable, allows the Council of Universities and the relevant public authorities to complete the initial accreditation and authorisation of the degree.

Because this ex-ante evaluation is centred on the study plan, it offers an appropriate framework to analyse how sustainability-related competences and learning outcomes are integrated into degree programmes. Within this procedure, universities must explicitly define these competences, as described above, embed them in the curriculum structure and teaching-learning strategies, and demonstrate that assessment methods and quality assurance mechanisms are aligned with their effective acquisition.

3.1.2 Monitoring and Modifications to existing degrees

Through a monitoring programme, carried out every three years, analyses and reports are generated for the various agents involved in the implementation and development of the degree programmes as a contribution to ensuring their quality.

On the other hand, after a degree has been developed for some time, universities may wish to introduce changes to its design and implementation, for example in relation to curriculum structure, learning outcomes

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or the inclusion of sustainability competences. In such cases, a formal modification proposal is submitted, which is evaluated using criteria equivalent to those applied to an initial verification report, so that substantial changes are externally reviewed as if they were part of a new programme design.

This modification procedure ensures that any significant redefinition of the programme, including the enhancement of sustainability learning outcomes, is consistent with quality standards and with the original accreditation framework. As a result, changes in the degree remain aligned with both national regulations and the reference standards used in the initial ex-ante accreditation.

3.1.3 Suggested modifications in ex-ante accreditation procedures

The following lines provide general guidelines to support quality assurance agency staff responsible for evaluation, ensuring that the criteria to be applied are clearly understood when reviewing documentation for new programme proposals or proposals for programme modification. It is possible that the following information should be to national agencies but provides general recommendations to be included in the national quality agencies guidelines.

Criterion – Organisation and Development

- Descriptor: The curriculum design and program organization must align with the degree profile and learning objectives, ensuring student-centered learning.
 - KPIs:
 - The self-assessment report must include the deployment of sustainability learning outcomes (LOs) based on the GreenComp framework.
 - A minimum of 8 sustainability LOs should be included, with corresponding teaching activities, methodologies, and evaluation systems.
 - Mechanisms to award the Green Stamp to students achieving these LOs should also be detailed.

Criterion – Learning Outcomes

- Descriptor: Teaching activities, methodologies, and evaluation systems must support the achievement of intended LOs.
 - KPI: Ensure that appropriate activities, teaching methods, and evaluation systems are in place to achieve sustainability's LOs.
- Descriptor: Achieved LOs must meet program objectives and correspond to the QF-EHEA (Qualifications Framework of the European Higher Education Area) level.
 - KPI: Present the distribution of sustainability LOs across the curriculum, specifying in which courses they are addressed.

Tables and Evidence

- Include a table listing GreenComp LOs per subject, the corresponding teaching activities, and evaluation system, following the example of Table 2.

3.2 Retrospective evaluation: ex-post accreditation

The Renewal of Accreditation of official degrees aims to verify whether the results of the degree are adequate and guarantee the continuity of its delivery until the next renewal of accreditation (every 6 years).

The legislation establishes that the initial accreditation of official degrees must be renewed periodically from the date of their verification or from the date of their last accreditation.

This procedure focuses on the normal implementation of the programme and provides evidence-based judgement on how the degree has actually operated over a full accreditation cycle.

External reviews of this kind examine whether the curriculum has been delivered as planned, whether students are achieving the intended learning outcomes, and whether resources, teaching staff and mobility arrangements remain adequate.

Evaluation criteria must observe the width and depth of incorporation of criteria and accomplishment of the KPIs exposed in the ex-ante evaluation. In addition, they must include a selection of evidence that supports given information.

This evidence can be considered as a non-exclusive list:

- Rubrics (based on those presented in the Greeniversity CORE).
- Deliverables.
- Exams.
- Translation of marks in subjects to recognition at degree level.

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4 Tips for implementation

Successful integration of **GreenComp competences** into university programs requires careful planning, collaboration, and practical strategies. The following tips provide guidance for universities seeking to embed sustainability competences effectively and achieve recognition as the so-called Green Stamp:

1. **Start with Curriculum Mapping.** Begin by mapping all courses against the GreenComp competences. Identify where each competence can be naturally integrated, especially in mandatory or core courses that all students take. Ensure coverage across all four competence areas: Embodying sustainability values, Embracing complexity in sustainability, Envisioning sustainable futures, and Acting for Sustainability.
2. **Prioritise Core Subjects for Competence Integration.** Incorporate at least eight of the twelve GreenComp competences into subjects that reach the majority of students, such as the obligatory. Where necessary, a single course can integrate up to two competences. Ensure that the learning outcomes are clearly defined for knowledge, skills, and attitudes to make evaluations straightforward.
3. **Use Active and Experiential Learning Methods.** Enhance competence development by employing teaching methods that go beyond lectures. Include case studies, project-based learning, simulations, fieldwork, or community engagement projects. These approaches promote transversal learning and help students apply sustainability competences in practical contexts. The Greeniversity project is providing a pedagogic guide, to be published, which can inspire and nurture the pedagogical approach at many areas of knowledge.
4. **Align Assessment with Competences.** Ensure that assessment methods reflect the intended learning outcomes. Each competence should be evaluated in at least two different courses whenever possible. Use the traffic-light evaluation system to track student progress in knowledge, skills, and attitudes, providing clear, quantifiable evidence for both internal monitoring and accreditation. Adaptation can be made according to each country's grade system. For example, on a scale of 0 to 10, red=0-4, yellow: 5-7, green: 8-10, or other options, according to the criteria of the degree's designers.
5. **Foster Faculty Collaboration and Training.** Provide workshops or professional development sessions for faculty members on sustainability education and GreenComp integration. Encourage interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure that competences are addressed consistently across different subjects and programs.
6. **Monitor Progress and Adjust.** Regularly review student performance data, curriculum implementation, and teaching methods. Use monitoring dashboards and internal evaluation tools to identify gaps or areas for improvement. Adjust course content, assessments, or teaching strategies as needed to maintain or improve competence integration.
7. **Engage Students in the Process.** Encourage students to actively participate in sustainability initiatives, feedback sessions, and project-based learning. Their engagement not only strengthens learning outcomes but also reinforces the university's commitment to sustainability and creates a culture of continuous improvement.
8. **Document Everything.** Maintain clear records of competence integration, assessment of outcomes, and any changes made to the courses. This documentation is essential for reaccreditation, monitoring, and external evaluations, providing transparent evidence that the program meets GreenComp standards.

By following these tips, universities can **streamline the integration of sustainability competences**, enhance student learning, and ensure that their programmes meet the criteria for the Green Stamp. Consequently, quality control by accreditation bodies will be straightforward and aligned. Implementation becomes a structured, manageable process that promotes long-term educational and societal impact.

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5 Conclusions

The transition from content-based teaching to a **competence-based model** is essential for addressing complex global challenges. The Greeniversity PATHWAY, together with the Greeniversity CORE moves beyond traditional knowledge acquisition by emphasizing the triad of **knowledge, skills, and attitudes**. By requiring students to demonstrate responsibility, autonomy, and ethical reasoning across four key competence areas—Values, Complexity, Futures, and Action—the approach ensures that graduates are not just technically proficient but are also capable of leading systemic change in professional and social contexts.

Quality assurance agencies are effective levers for systemic change. By embedding sustainability criteria into both **ex-ante (verification)** and **ex-post (monitoring and renewal)** accreditation processes, the Pathway ensures that green competences are rigorously evaluated and maintained. This dual approach transforms sustainability from a theoretical ambition into a mandatory requirement for degree design, forcing institutions to demonstrate clear coherence between curriculum structure, teaching methodologies, and measurable learning outcomes.

To ensure transparency and accountability, the PATHWAY proposes a robust **traffic-light evaluation system** that quantifies the integration of sustainability. The creation of a **Green Stamp** or special certification within the European Supplement to the Title provides a clear incentive for both students and institutions to strive for excellence. This measurable system allows for a standardized assessment across diverse disciplines and national borders, providing employers and society with a reliable indicator of a graduate's ability to navigate and solve environmental and social problems.

In this context, the **Greeniversity PATHWAY** provides straightforward guidelines for integrating GreenComp competences into higher education programmes and for supporting universities and quality assurance agencies in the evaluation and accreditation process. By aligning curricula with sustainability competences, institutions can equip students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to address pressing environmental and societal challenges. In this sense, it supports **evidence-based decision-making for evaluation committees**, enabling agencies and reviewers to assess programmes against consistent criteria, monitor quality, and provide actionable feedback. The report also highlights the importance of **coordination, monitoring, and practical tools** to effectively integrate sustainability in the core of the HE programs.

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